

RULES OF GENERAL PROPERTY IN ENGLISH.

(PASSIVE VOICE)

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the infinitive, how to form it, changes in tenses, the rules of proper use of auxiliary verbs, and the third form of the main verb.

INGLIZ TILIDA MAJHUL NISBATNI HOSIL QILISH QOIDALARI.

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Yordamchi fe'llar, majhul nisbat, to'g'ri va noto'g'ri fe'llar, zamonlarga oid signal so'zlar, egali gaplar, egasiz gaplar.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada majhul nisbat, uni qanday hosil qilish, zamonlardagi o'zgarishlar, yordamchi fe'llardan to'g'ri foydalanish qoidalari hamda asosiy fe'lning uchinchi shakli haqida ma'lumot beriladi.

Ma'lumki, o'zbek tilida fe'lning bir nechta nisbat shakllari mavjud. Aniq nisbat,

majhul nisbat, orttirma nisbat, o'zlik nisbat kabilar shular jumlasidandir. Bular orasida

majhul nisbat - fe'ning o'ziga xos shakli bo'lib, ingliz tilida bu shaklni hosil qilishning ma'lum talab va qoidalari bor. Majhul nisbatni hosil qilishda eng kerakli unsur deb yordamchi fe'llarni aytish mumkin. Yordamchi fe'llar gapdagi zamon shakliga qarab o'zgarib boradi. Bundan tashqari majhul nisbatni hosil qilishda noto'g'ri fe'llar jadvalidan yaxshi xabardor bo'lish talab etiladi. Boisi, biz yordamchi fe'ldan keyin asosiy fe'ning uchinchi shaklidan foydalanamiz. To'g'ri fe'llarga -ed qo'shimchasini qo'shish orqali ularni uchinchi shaklga aylantirish mumkin. Noto'g'ri fe'llarni esa maxsus jadvaldan yodlab olishimiz maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Ingliz tilida gaplar ikki xil bo'ladi.

- 1) Aktiv gaplar
- 2) Passiv gaplar

Aktiv gaplarda ega ishtirok etadi. Ma'lum bir yumush ma'lum shaxs tomonidan bajariladi. Asosiy urg'u kim bajarganligiga qaratiladi.

Passiv gaplarda esa aksincha. Ega ishtirok etmaydi. Ma'lum bir yumush bajariladi, lekin uni kim tomonidan bajarilganligi emas, shunchaki bajarilganligi urg'u oladi.

Hozirgi oddiy zamon shaklidagi gaplarni majhul nisbat shakliga aylantirib ko'ramiz.

Present Simple

Lucy cleans this room every day.

(Lucy bu xonani har kuni tozalaydi). -

Aktiv gap

This room is cleaned every day.

(Bu xona har kuni tozalanadi). -Passiv gap. [Raymond Murphy. Four edition. Unit 42. Passiv 1]

Bu misoldan kelib chiqib, formula yaratishimiz mumkin.

S + tobe + verb3

Ya'ni Aktiv gapdagi to'ldiruvchi Passiv gapga o'tganda biz uni shartli ravishta gapning egasi deb qabul qilamiz. Lucy cleans this room every day. Bu - Aktiv gap hisoblanadi va bu yerda This room - to'ldiruvchi. Agar biz bu gapni Passiv shakliga aylantirsak, to'ldiruvchi gapning boshiga o'tadi va ega vazifasini bajaradi. This room is cleaned every day. Xuddi shu tartibda.

NATIJALAR

Passiv gaplarni hosil qilishda fe'llar katta ahamiyatga ega. Aytib o'tganimizdek bizga fe'llarning uchinchi shakli kerak bo'ladi. To'g'ri fe'llarga -ed qo'shimchasini qo'shish orqali ularni uchinchi shaklga aylantiramiz.

Masalan, clean - cleaned, work - worked, want - wanted, wash - washed, damage - damaged, invent - invented, invite - invited, surround - surrounded, translate - translated, pronounce - pronounced, cause - caused...

Noto'g'ri fe'llarning uchinchi shaklini esa maxsus jadvaldan yodlab olishimiz lozim.

Masalan, be - been, go - gone, do - done, see - seen, write - written, send - sent, fly - flown, make - made, hold - held, take - taken, give - given, grow - grown, buy - bought, bring - brought, steal - stolen, have - had...

MUHOKAMA

This room is cleaned every day. - Present Simple

This room was cleaned yesterday. - Past Simple

This room is being cleaned now. - Present Continuous

This room was being cleaned when I came. - Past Continuous

This room has been cleaned. - Present Perfect

This room had been cleaned when I came. - Past Perfect

This room will be cleaned. - Future Simple

If Lucy had time, this room would be cleaned. - Conditionals

This room must be cleaned. - Modals
XULOSA

Majhul nisbatdagi gaplarni hosil qilish u darajada murakkab emas. Faqat biroz e'tibor bilan yodlash talab etiladi. Noto'g'ri fe'llarning uchinchi shaklini noto'g'ri fe'llar jadvalidan yodlab olish va yordamchi fe'llarni ham yodda saqlash adashish yoki chalkashtirib yuborishni oldini oladi. Mavzuni qoidalarga amal qilgan holda o'zlashtirish ingliz tilidagi majhul nisbatni qiyinchiliksiz o'rganish, yozuvda hamda nutqda erkin ishlata olishga zamin yaratadi.

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